

Supplemental Material for “The common patterns of abundance: the log series and Zipf’s law”

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Discrete and continuous probability distributions are usually analyzed differently, which prevents a general understanding of scale. These notes present a technique by which a change of variable or a change of scale can be done in a consistent way for both discrete and continuous distributions [1]. The final section relates discrete and continuous scales, illustrated by the log series.

For example, suppose initial measurements are in terms of abundance, n , and we wish to analyze the data on the transformed logarithmic scale, $r = \log n$. How can we make the change of variable, $n \mapsto e^r$, consistently for discrete and continuous cases?

The Dirac delta function provides the basis for a consistent method. The next section introduces the basic aspects and notation for the Dirac delta function. The following section shows how to use this method to obtain a consistent approach for transforming scale by change of variable. The final sections consider transformations between discrete and continuous variables and the specification of the domains of variables.

I. DIRAC DELTA FUNCTION

The Dirac delta function, δ , provides the key. The function is defined such that

$$\int_{-\epsilon}^{\epsilon} \delta(z) dz = 1$$

for any real value $\epsilon > 0$. In other words, for any region of integration containing 0, the integral of $\delta(z)$ is one. Then we also have

$$\int_{z-\epsilon}^{z+\epsilon} f(x) \delta(x-z) dx = f(z).$$

In other words, the integral picks out the function evaluated at the point $x = z$, at which $\delta(x-z) = \delta(0)$.

With that definition, we can write a discrete probability distribution at the set of points $\Omega = \{x_i\}$ as a continuous probability density function

$$f(x) \sum_{x_i \in \Omega} \delta(x - x_i) = f(x) \delta_x, \quad (1)$$

because the cumulative distribution function, $F(x)$, of the continuous density, $f(x) \delta_x$, has the form of a discrete probability distribution

$$F(a) = \int_{-\infty}^{a+\epsilon} f(x) \delta_x dx = \sum_{x_i \in \Omega} f(x_i),$$

in which $x_i < a + \epsilon$ for an infinitesimal positive value, ϵ . We need the extra ϵ so that δ_x integrates to one around a point $x_i = a$,

For continuous distributions, let the density of points in Ω increase to fill the interval $(-\infty, \infty)$ continuously. Then

$$\delta_x = \sum_{x_i \in \Omega} \delta(x - x_i) \rightarrow \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \delta(x - x_i) dx_i = 1,$$

because, whatever the value of x , there will be some point $x_i \in \Omega$ for which $x = x_i$, and any integral over the region including that point is one. With $\delta_x = 1$, the continuous probability density function is $f(x)$, and the cumulative distribution function is

$$F(a) = \int_{-\infty}^{a+\epsilon} f(x) dx = \int_{-\infty}^a f(x) dx,$$

because $\int_a^{a+\epsilon} f(x) dx = 0$ for infinitesimal ϵ and finite $f(x)$.

II. CHANGE OF VARIABLE

I seek a consistent method for doing a change of variable in both continuous and discrete probability distributions. The approach arises from always considering the probability associated with a value as the area of a rectangle.

For a continuous distributions, we write $f(x) dx$, which is the product of the probability function, f , as the height, and the infinitesimal interval, dx , as the width. Thus, the probability in the interval $(a, a + \epsilon)$, with small width ϵ , is

$$\int_a^{a+\epsilon} f(x) dx \approx f(a) \epsilon,$$

the product of the height, $f(a)$, and the width, ϵ . When we change variables, $x \mapsto g(x) \equiv y$, we obtain both a

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new height, $f(y)$, and a new width, dy , and so we must compensate appropriately, as shown below.

For discrete distributions, we may write $f(x)\Delta x$, in which Δx is the width associated with a discrete point, x . Typically, we assume that $\Delta x = 1$ for all x , and write the discrete probability as $f(x)$. We can think of this as the area of a rectangle with implicit width of one.

When we change variables, $x \mapsto g(x) \equiv y$, traditionally one keeps the interval widths, $\Delta y = 1$, as one on the new scale, y , and the probabilities are simply $f(y)$ at the new points, y . However, by changing scales, the spacing between the discrete points on the y scale differs from the spacing between points on the original x scale.

This change of spacing can be interpreted as a change in the widths associated with discrete probability points, or as a change in the density of probability points in intervals along the y scale. Thus, as in the continuous case, we may wish to keep track of how both the heights change, $f(x) \mapsto f(y)$, and how the widths change with a change of scale, $\Delta x \mapsto \Delta y$. Doing so provides a consistent way of changing variables for continuous and discrete cases.

I begin with the standard method for continuous variables. I then demonstrate an analogous method for discrete variables based on the Dirac delta function.

For a continuous distribution, $f(x)$, I make the change $x \mapsto g(x) \equiv y$. With that transformation, we have

$$dy/dx = g'(x).$$

Define

$$m_y = \frac{1}{|g'(x)|},$$

in which the absolute value arises because we are using dx and dy as positive probability measures. Thus,

$$dx = m_y dy.$$

Then the standard result for the change of variable $x \mapsto y$ in a continuous distribution yields

$$f(x)dx = f(y)m_y dy. \quad (2)$$

For discrete distributions, I will derive the analogous change of variable expression

$$f(x)\delta_x dx = f(y)m_y \delta'_y dy = f(y)\delta_y dy. \quad (3)$$

To obtain this result, we need to show that the change of variable $x \mapsto g(x) \equiv y$ leads to

$$\delta_x dx \mapsto m_y \delta'_y dy = \delta_y dy,$$

which follows if

$$\delta_x \mapsto m_y^{-1} \delta_y \equiv \delta'_y.$$

To obtain this expression for δ'_y , we need the general change of variable rule for the Dirac delta function

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(x - x_i) &\mapsto |g'(x_i)| \delta[g(x) - g(x_i)] \\ &= m_y^{-1} \delta(y - y_i). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, with $\Omega' = \{g(x_i)\} = \{y_i\}$, we have

$$\delta_x = \sum_{x_i \in \Omega} \delta(x - x_i) \mapsto m_y^{-1} \sum_{y_i \in \Omega'} \delta(y - y_i) = m_y^{-1} \delta_y.$$

III. THE GAMMA AND LOG SERIES DISTRIBUTIONS

The gamma distribution is given by the probability function

$$f(x) = kx^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda x},$$

in which the constant k normalizes the total probability to be one. With $\alpha = 0$ and $x > x_0 > 0$ for x_0 not too close to zero, this has the same mathematical form as the log series distribution.

Consider the change in variable $r = \log x = g(x)$, which corresponds to $x \mapsto e^r$. Then,

$$|g'(x)| = d \log x / dx = 1/x = e^{-r} = m_r^{-1}.$$

If we consider $f(x)$ as a continuous distribution, then we can apply the formula for change of variable in eqn 2 to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} f(x)dx &= f(r)m_r dr \\ &= ke^{r(\alpha-1)} e^{-\lambda e^r} e^r dr \\ &= ke^{r\alpha - \lambda e^r} dr \\ &= h(r)dr, \end{aligned}$$

in which

$$h(r) = f(r)m_r = ke^{r\alpha - \lambda e^r}, \quad (4)$$

for $r > \log x_0$. For $\alpha = 0$, transforming the log series form

$$f(x) = kx^{-1} e^{-\lambda x}$$

by $r = \log x$ yields the equivalent distribution on the r scale as

$$h(r) = ke^{-\lambda e^r}. \quad (5)$$

Now consider $f(x)$ as a discrete distribution. Then, by eqn 3, we immediately have

$$f(x)\delta_x dx = f(r)m_r \delta'_r dr = h(r)\delta'_r dr,$$

in which the full form of $h(r)$ is given in eqn 4, and we also have the log series form with $\alpha = 0$ in eqn 5.

Thus, by using the measure dr for the widths in the continuous case and the measure $\delta'_r dr$ for the widths in the discrete case, we obtain the identical probability function $h(r)$ for the continuous and discrete cases.

For the discrete case, we must keep in mind that

$$h(r)\delta'_r dr = h(r)m_r^{-1} \delta_r dr,$$

in which the right side is the traditional expression that picks out the probability mass, $h(r)m_r^{-1}$, as the heights at the points defined by $\delta_r dr$, implicitly using constant widths of one on all scales, because at a discrete point, r^* , at which the probability is nonzero,

$$\int_{r^*-\epsilon}^{r^*+\epsilon} \delta_r dr = 1.$$

In the gamma example, $m_r^{-1} = e^{-r}$, with $x = 1, 2, \dots$ and $r = \log 1, \log 2, \dots$, we have the traditional expression for a discrete change of variable with constant widths of one as

$$\begin{aligned} f(x)\delta_x dx &\mapsto h(r)m_r^{-1}\delta_r dr \\ &= ke^{r(\alpha-1)-\lambda e^r}\delta_r dr. \end{aligned}$$

For the log series case, $\alpha = 0$, this becomes

$$h(r)m_r^{-1}\delta_r dr = ke^{-r-\lambda e^r}\delta_r dr.$$

We can go back to the classic log series expression by reversing the change, $e^r \mapsto n$, yielding the discrete distribution $f(n)\delta_n dn$ for $n = 1, 2, \dots$, with

$$f(n) = kn^{-1}e^{-\lambda n}.$$

In these examples, I have assumed that the distributions on the r and $n \equiv x$ scales are either both discrete or both continuous. In application, it will usually make sense to think of process, r , as a continuous variable, and abundance, n , as a discrete variable. Therefore, we need to consider transformations between continuous and discrete variables. I discuss that topic in the final section, after a brief summary of the discrete transformations.

IV. SUMMARY OF ALTERNATIVE DISCRETE EXPRESSIONS

We have two different ways of expressing transformed discrete variables, in which the initial distribution is given by $f(x)\delta_x dx$, and we transform $x \mapsto y$.

In the first expression, the transformed distribution is

$$f(y)m_y\delta'_y dy = h(y)\delta'_y dy,$$

in which $h(y) = f(y)m_y$ is the same expression as obtained when transforming continuous variables. The measure for the y scale, $\delta'_y dy$, stretches or shrinks in relation to the measure for the x scale, altering the widths associated with each height. This form has the advantage of retaining the same expressions for the probability functions in the discrete and continuous cases.

In the second expression, the transformed distribution is

$$f(y)\delta_y dy = h(y)m_y^{-1}\delta_y dy,$$

in which this expression highlights the difference between the standard form of the probability function obtained in the discrete case, $f(y) = h(y)m_y^{-1}$, and the standard form of the probability function obtained in the continuous case, $h(y) = f(y)m_y$. Here, we assume the widths associated with each probability point remain one on all scales.

For the transformation $x \mapsto g(x) \equiv y$, the value $m_y^{-1} = |g'(x)|$ determines the distinction between the discrete and continuous cases, associated with the change in widths between scales.

V. TRANSFORMING BETWEEN CONTINUOUS AND DISCRETE VARIABLES

In the prior cases, we transformed from one discrete variable to another discrete variable or from one continuous variable to another continuous variable. The expressions for transformation followed without any further assumptions.

In the case of the log series and the distribution of abundances, it often make sense to consider process, r , as a continuous variable, and abundance, n , as a discrete variable. We usually think of process as causing abundance. So we should begin with the continuous distribution for process, q_r , and seek the corresponding discrete distribution for abundance, q_n .

The probability mass, q_n , at a particular value of $n = 1, 2, \dots$, should map to the total probability for a matching range of growth rates, such that

$$q_n = \int_{a_n}^{b_n} q_r dr, \quad (6)$$

in which $r > a_1$.

We need the particular form of q_r , which we take as the fundamental shift-invariant distribution in the main text

$$q_r = ke^{-\lambda e^r}. \quad (7)$$

We also need, for each n , the interval of growth rates, (a_n, b_n) , that maps to the abundance, n . In particular, we need a sequence of contiguous intervals, $\{(a_n, b_n)\}$, that associate each value of n to an interval for r , such that $a_{n+1} = b_n$.

The problem concerns how to pick the sequence of intervals. The simplest approach is to use a standard rounding procedure, such that

$$\begin{aligned} a_n &= \log(n - 0.5 + \gamma) \\ b_n &= \log(n + 0.5 + \gamma), \end{aligned}$$

in which $\gamma < 0.5$ is a correction for centering intervals to account for the nonlinearity in the mapping between the continuous and discrete probability expressions.

If we use $\gamma = 0.1$, the transformation from the continuous scale r to the discrete scale n in eqn 6 yields a

FIG. 1. Close match between the continuous distribution for process, r , and the discrete log series for abundance, n . The blue circles show the probabilities of the discrete values of n obtained from the continuous distribution in r , calculated by eqn 6. The gold circles show the actual values of q_n for the log series in eqn 8. For most points, the values are nearly identical, causing the gold circles to hide the underlying blue circles. (a) When using no offset for continuous intervals, $\gamma = 0$, a slight mismatch occurs, particularly at $n = 1$. The nonlinearity of q_r causes the mismatch. (b) When using an offset of $\gamma = 0.1$, the continuous distribution of the process, r , maps almost perfectly onto the discrete log series of abundance, n . For all calculations, $\lambda = 0.05$.

distribution that closely matches the log series

$$q_n \approx kn^{-1}e^{-\lambda n}. \quad (8)$$

Figure 1 shows the match between the continuous distri-

bution for r and the associated discrete distribution for n .

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- [1] C. Au and J. Tam, Transforming variables using the Dirac generalized function, *The American Statistician* **53**, 270 (1999).